

Introduction

This document provides an overview of resources created in relation to the Horizon Europe-funded project HealthyPlants (grant ID: 101106728). All resources described below are publicly available and accessible.

Aim of the document

Plant viruses are one of the main threats to European agriculture. Their impact is being increased due to climate change and pesticide resistance. Hence, the need for a robust integrated pest management system is growing. Effective disease management depends on rapid, sensitive and specific diagnostic tools built on a clear understanding of viral diversity and their presence not only in crops, but also in potential reservoirs in the agro-ecological landscape.

This project provides knowledge and tools necessary for molecular surveillance of plant viruses in Ireland. This goal is achieved through: (1) completing the first survey of viruses associated with major cultivated plants in Ireland and establish an open, national baseline of viral sequences to underpin development of new diagnostic and surveillance tools; (2) determining whether field margins, hedgerows and pastures act as reservoirs for cereal and other crop viruses; and (3) screening newly imported tuber crops with potential phytosanitary risks.

The resources provided below constitute the database of viral sequences detected in crops and in potential reservoirs (arable margins and pastures), as well as the results of screening newly imported tuber crops.

Overview

The project's database main output consists of two main tables: the list of samples with associated metadata, and the list of confirmed plant viruses. Not all collected samples were sequenced during the project duration. Whenever the samples are sequenced, the relevant BioSample is provided and, in case of existing assemblies, the GenBank accession ID is also provided. Information about BioSample and GenBank assemblies is provided both from the perspective of a sample and of a plant virus.

The overview of metadata and associated information is provided on the graph below.

Figure 1. The relationship between main data types. Two important values are: Sample ID and identified Plant virus.

The links to the databases are provided in the section below, together with additional resources. We encourage you to take a look at the available materials.

Details and links

Databases:

Sample ID-oriented database: [10.5281/zenodo.18938106](https://zenodo.org/record/18938106)

Plant virus-oriented database: [10.5281/zenodo.18938157](https://zenodo.org/record/18938157)

Materials:

Photographs: [10.5281/zenodo.18938349](https://zenodo.org/record/18938349)

Bioinformatics analysis overview:

General overview of the bioinformatics analysis of 150bp paired-end Illumina reads of plant material with putative viral content

1. QC of raw data

- a. Tool: FASTQC v0.12.1¹ (using multiQC² to generate combined report for multiple samples)
2. Trimming reads
 - a. Tool: Cutadapt -5.2³
 - b. Options: trimming universal Illumina adapters
3. QC of trimmed reads
 - a. Tool: FASTQC v0.12.1
4. Mapping reads to the host genome (**optional**; only in case of known, single host - crop samples)
 - a. Tool: BWA⁴ 0.7.17
 - b. Options: collecting unmapped reads for downstream analysis
5. Taxonomic profiling
 - a. Tool: KRAKEN2⁵ 2.1.3
 - b. Database used: PlusPFP, January, 2024. Downloaded from <https://benlangmead.github.io/aws-indexes/k2>
 - c. Additional options: Extracting reads matching to Viruses and taxons within this group using the script from KrakenTools⁶: <https://github.com/jenniferlu717/KrakenTools>
6. De novo assembly
 - a. Tool: SPAdes⁷ 4.0.0
 - b. Options: meta
 - c. Additional options: Performed using a subset of reads extracted at step 5
7. Reference based assembly
 - a. BWA and/or Geneious 2025.2
 - b. Additional options: Performed using a subset of reads extracted at step 5.

Laboratory protocols:

1. Isolation of dsRNA from Plants by Cellulose Chromatography (viral enrichment method):
2. RT-LAMP for beet yellows virus detection:
<https://www.protocols.io/view/rt-lamp-for-byv-detection-261geeo1og47/>
 (doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.261geeo1og47/v1>)

¹ Andrews, S. (2010). FastQC: A Quality Control Tool for High Throughput Sequence Data [Online]. Available online at: <http://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc/>

² Ewels, P. et al., (2016). MultiQC: Summarize analysis results for multiple tools and samples in a single report. *Bioinformatics* (2016). doi: 10.1093/bioinformatics/btw354

³ Martin, M. (2011). Cutadapt removes adapter sequences from high-throughput sequencing reads. *EMBnet. journal*, 17(1), 10-12. doi:10.14806/ej.17.1.200

⁴ Li H. (2013) Aligning sequence reads, clone sequences and assembly contigs with BWA-MEM. arXiv:1303.3997v2.

⁵ Wood DE, Lu J, Langmead B. Improved metagenomic analysis with Kraken 2 (2019). *Genome Biology*. 2019 Nov;p. 76230

⁶ Lu J. et al., (2022):. Metagenome analysis using the Kraken software suite. *Nature Protocols*, doi: 10.1038/s41596-022-00738-y

⁷ Nurk S. et al., (2017). metaSPAdes: a new versatile metagenomic assembler. *Genome research*, 27.5: 824-834. doi: 10.1101/gr.213959.116

List of publications:

1. Niedzicka M., Alves S., McNamara L., Byrne S. (under review): A note on potential viral threats to legume crops in Ireland.
2. Niedzicka, M., & Byrne, S. (2026). Investigating plant viruses present in alternative tubers. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18162195>
3. Niedzicka M., Ballandras V., McNamara L., Byrne S. (2025): First report of soybean dwarf virus in clover species in Ireland. New Disease Reports: <https://doi.org/10.1002/ndr2.70017>
4. Niedzicka M. (2025): Soybean Dwarf Virus. Plant Health Cases 2025, phcs20250028: <https://doi.org/10.1079/planthealthcases.2025.0028>
5. Pimenta R., Niedzicka M., Byrne S., Rathore D. (2025): First report of ash shoestring-associated virus infecting common ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*) in Ireland. New Disease Reports: <https://doi.org/10.1002/ndr2.70062>
6. Niedzicka M., Kildea S., Byrne S. (2025): Comparison of DNA-seq and RNA-seq in plant microbiome identification on rye - a case study. Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17725159>
7. Niedzicka, M., Mc Namara, L., & Byrne, S. (2025). Insect-transmitted plant viruses across crops and viral reservoirs in Ireland. Irish Entomologists' Meeting, University College Dublin. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17854123>
8. Niedzicka, M., Virgile, B., Mc Namara, L., & Byrne, S. (2025). Using HTS to understand viral diversity in arable margins and its impact on various crops. International Advances in Plant Virology (IAPV25), Murcia, Spain. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16026949>
9. Niedzicka, M., Mc Namara, L., & Byrne, S. (2024). Comparison of dsRNA and rRNA depleted RNA methods for virome studies in complex plant communities. Plant Pathology 2024 (PPATH2024), University of Oxford. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16026701>

Additional resources

Media articles:

- “5 ways viruses can help plants”, RTE Brainstorm: <https://www.rte.ie/brainstorm/2025/0205/1494846-5-ways-viruses-can-help-plants/>
- “New BYDV guidelines on the way”, Irish Farmers Journal based on National Tillage Conference 2026 presentation: <https://www.farmersjournal.ie/tillage/news/new-bydv-guidelines-on-the-way-902483>
- “Research, or there and back again”, 43rd MCAA Newsletter, Sustainable Career Transition Pathway: Bridging Academia, Public Sector, and Industry Special Issue: <https://www.mariecuriealumni.eu/newsletters/43rd-mcaa-newsletter/special-issue-research-or-there-and-back-again>

Contact

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